

equations for $g(\kappa)$ viz. $-\ln(1-\kappa)$, $[-\ln(1-\kappa)]^{1/2}$ and $[-\ln(1-\kappa)]^{1/3}$ gave linear relations, only the one corresponding to the Mampel model equation⁹, i.e. $(1-\kappa)$ for $f(\kappa)$, gave reasonable values of frequency factor and activation energy. The order of magnitude of frequency factor according to this model equation is agreeably close to theoretical requirement⁹. The moderately negative entropy of activation ($-71 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$) indicates formation of an ordered transition state. It is likely that the complex decomposes by random nucleation, i.e. with formation of a nucleus on every particle.

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Studies on Schiff Bases of Veratraldehyde

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A survey of literature¹⁻³ showed that study of Schiff bases of veratraldehyde has not been carried out so far. It was, therefore, of interest to synthesize new Schiff bases derived from veratraldehyde. This paper describes the synthesis of veratraldehyde Schiff bases, their sodium borohydride reduction products, spectral studies of the

Schiff bases and their reduced products, and fungicidal activity of Schiff bases and the secondary amines.

The Schiff bases have been prepared in quantitative yields by condensing equimolar quantities of veratraldehyde and aromatic amines (aniline and substituted anilines) in toluene by azeotropic distillation of water formed during the reaction. The Schiff bases having *m*-NO₂ and *o*-OCH₃ groups are dark coloured thick oils.

The uv spectra of the Schiff bases give four absorption bands at 213, 235, 270 and 335 nm. It has been found that the absorption bands (band II at 235 nm and band IV at 335 nm) are sensitive to N-phenyl substitution while the other two bands (band I at 213 nm and band III at 270 nm) usually remain unaffected. Band at ~270 nm is the characteristic band of >C=N- as is shown by the fact that this band completely disappears on reduction of the >C=N- linkage with sodium borohydride. In ir, >C=N- absorption is observed at ~1625 cm⁻¹.

Reduction of veratraldehyde Schiff bases has been carried out with sodium borohydride in methanol at 60-65°. The use of higher temperature is partly required because of low solubility of the Schiff bases in methanol. The reduction is not possible in case of Schiff bases having hydroxyl group in the N-phenyl ring and it is suppressed in case of 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*o*-anisidine because of steric hindrance.

A study of the spectra of the reduced products in conjugation with those of the parent Schiff bases reveals that the absorption bands assigned to >C=N- linkage (~270 nm) are absent in the spectra of the reduced products. The ir spectra of the dihydro products lack the absorption bands (~1625 cm⁻¹) assigned to >C=N-, but contain additional bands (3440-3420 cm⁻¹) due to NH group.

The Schiff bases and their reduced products as well as the uv spectra of the Schiff bases are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS OF VERATRALDEHYDE SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR DIHYDRO PRODUCTS

Sl. No.	Substituent in N-phenyl ring	m.p. (°C) of		UV Spectra of the Schiff Bases of Veratraldehyde			
		Schiff Base	Dihydro Product	Band I MeOH λ _{max} (nm)(log e)	Band II MeOH λ _{max} (nm)(log e)	Band III MeOH λ _{max} (nm)(log e)	Band IV MeOH λ _{max} (nm)(log e)
1.	H	83	92	218 (4.03)	235 (4.28)	268 (4.39)	335 (4.83)
2.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	116	87	209 (4.18)	—	270 (4.16)	337 (5.04)
3.	<i>p</i> -OH	99	110	210 (3.85)	281 (4.12)	267 (4.38)	345 (4.38)
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	126	137	211 (4.30)	242 (4.18)	269 (4.36)	350 (4.30)
5.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	97	60	211 (4.30)	242 (4.16)	270 (4.44)	350 (4.40)
6.	<i>o</i> -OH	100	—	303 (4.53)	242 (4.32)	262 (3.34)	355 (3.84)
7.	<i>m</i> -OH	215	—	210 (4.24)	248 (4.28)	270 (4.31)	355 (3.83)
8.	<i>m</i> -Cl	80	123	211 (3.85)	—	268 (3.35)	330 (3.15)
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl	83	124	211 (3.45)	—	268 (4.37)	336 (4.21)
10.	<i>p</i> -Br	99	107	210 (4.34)	—	270 (4.44)	346 (4.23)
11.	<i>o</i> -OOH	oil	100	209 (4.21)	230 (4.10)	269 (4.40)	348 (4.20)
12.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	oil	141	—	—	268 (5.54)	—

All the melting points are uncorrected. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses and yields were excellent.

The 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines were subjected to *in vitro*, activity test against various fungi. The Schiff bases having electron-donating substituents in the N-phenyl ring have shown remarkable activity against the fungi *Alternaria solani* and *Colletotrichum capsici*. Similar test of secondary amines have indicated that though they are active against the above mentioned fungi, they are less effective than the Schiff bases.

Experimental

Synthesis of 3,4-dimethoxybenzalaniline : A mixture of veratraldehyde (0.1 mole), aniline (0.1 mole) and toluene (125 ml) was refluxed till water (0.1 mole) had separated out. Distillation of the solvent gave a crude Schiff base which was recrystallised from methanol as white shining crystals, m.p. 83° (yield 100%).

Reduction of 3,4-dimethoxybenzalaniline : To a stirred solution of 3,4-dimethoxybenzalaniline (0.1 mole) in methanol (50 ml) was added an alkaline solution of sodium borohydride (2.0 g in 2 ml of 2 N NaOH diluted to 20 ml with distilled water) dropwise at a rate so as to keep the temperature between 50-60°. The contents were then cooled and kept overnight at room temperature. The excess of solvent was distilled off, the contents were cooled, diluted with water (100 ml), chilled in ice bath for 2 hr and filtered. The crude product was then recrystallised from methanol to give light yellow shining needles, m.p. 92° (yield 80%).

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Synthesis of 9-Alkyl-6-Mercaptopurine Analogues

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6-MERCAPTOPYRINE (6MP)¹, an antimetabolite with relatively low toxicity is widely used clinically to treat leukemia. The activity of 6MP substituted at the 9-position with normal alkyl and cycloalkyl groups were studied² earlier against a line of H. Ep2 cells and two sublines resistant to 6MP. It was found that the butyl, pentyl, cyclopentyl, hexyl, cyclohexyl, heptyl and octyl derivatives exerted inhibitory effect on all the 3 lines.

Friend Leukemia virus infection in mice was inhibited by 9-cyclopentyl-6-mercaptopurine³. It was of interest to study the effect of long chain alkyl substitution at 9-position of 6MP on tumour as it was observed that lipophilicity sometimes increased the activity of an anticancer drug when it could be modified by appropriate substitution⁴. This communication describes the synthesis of 9-undecyl (I), dodecyl (II), tetradecyl (III), hexadecyl (IV) and

Fig. 1. I. R=C₁₁H₂₃; II. R=C₁₂H₂₅; III. R=C₁₄H₂₉; IV. R=C₁₆H₃₃; V. R=C₁₈H₃₇

octadecyl 6-mercaptopurine (V) and studies on their effect *in vitro* against KB cells and *in vivo* against lymphoid leukemia L1210 and Sarcoma-180.

The above 6MP analogues were prepared by reacting thiourea in *n*-propanol with the corresponding 6-chloro-9-alkyl purines whose synthesis has been reported earlier⁵.

Experimental

The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes using a Thomas-Hoover Unimelt apparatus and are uncorrected. The ultraviolet spectra in ethanol and the infra red spectra in KBr were recorded in Pye Unicam SP8 100 and Perkin Elmer 177 spectrophotometer respectively. The experimental procedure being similar, the preparation of 9-undecyl 6-mercaptopurine is described here as a representative case.

6-Mercapto-9-undecyl purine (I) : A solution of 322 mg (1.04 mmole) of 6-chloro-9-undecyl purine⁵ and 100 mg (1.32 mmole) of thiourea in 10 ml *n*-propanol was heated under reflux for 1 hr and then cooled in ice bath. The precipitated solid was collected by filtration, washed with cold *n*-propanol and dried; yield 230 mg (72.0%), m.p. 260-64°. Two crystallisations of the crude material from ethanol gave the analytical sample (I), m.p. 265-66°. λ_{max} in nm 324. ν in cm⁻¹ (KBr): 2800-2000 (acidic hydrogen); 1600 and 1540 (C=C and C=N).

The physical characteristics of the different compounds prepared are given in Table 1.

Biological assay : All these mercapto compounds were tested against Sarcoma-180 in strain A mice. *In vitro* testings in KB cells and *in vivo* in lymphoid leukemia L1210 were carried out at National Cancer Institute, USA. None of the compounds, however, showed antitumour activity.

In vitro tests in KB cells showed ED₅₀ to be 1.0 × 10³ µg/ml for all the compounds, the criteria of activity being ED₅₀ ≤ 6 µg/ml. *In vivo* tests against Lymphoid Leukemia L1210 were carried out in BDF₁ mice at 5 different dose levels viz., 400,